

Single-Stage Deep Drawing Process Simulation Study of AISI 304 Stainless Steel Using AFDEX Software

Rohan Kattimani¹, Prof. Vijayendra B. Hippargi²

¹ Student, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Visvesvarya Technological University, Kalaburagi, India
kattimani88@gmail.com

² Associate, professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Visvesvarya University, Kalaburagi India,
vijaybh1965@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this research, we will investigate the material behavior of AISI 304 stainless steel in single phase deep drawing and the factors effecting. AISI 304 is amongst prevalent materials for deep drawing due to its versatility and high quality. In addition, the characteristics that affect AISI 304's deep drawability will be identified. SolidEdge V19 is used for the design and modeling of molds and workpieces. Using AFDEX, this process can be simulated and analyzed. Frictional coefficient & die corner radius are the independent factors in this study. Consistency is maintained in both the punch velocity (230mm/s) and the BHF (1265N). The cold forming type allows for a steady 25 degrees Celsius.

Key words: AFDEX, Solid Edge V19, Die corner Radius, Co-efficient of friction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep drawing is a common industrial method for shaping metal sheets into containers like cups and boxes. Many kitchen and bathroom essentials, as well as automotive parts like panels and gas tanks, are created through the sheet metal deep drawing process. Drawing is the process used in the metalworking industry to mould flat sheets of metal into hollow forms by punching them and allowing them to flow in cavity of a mold. When the depth is equal to or more than the diameter, a deep pull is performed.

Deep drawing on sheet metal is achieved using punches and dies. After the outline of the part's base has been drawn, it is punched out. To allow for clearance and movement of the punch, the die chamber is larger than the punch itself. This setup is quite similar to a sheet metal cutter in many respects. When cutting, clearance refers to the distance between the die edge and the punch edge. A metal blank is a flat piece of metal that is cut using a die. The blank holder presses whole blank surface against punch when working with flat sheet metal. The dice is contained in a blank holder. The punctuation mark approaches the blank. A metal sheet is punctured by an impact punch and then shoved into a die cavity.

Keeping the drawing's shape as simple as feasible is recommended while constructing a deep drawing. In the initial phase of deep drawing sheet metal, the base of the item will be flat.

Figure 1: Deep Drawing Method

II. LITERATURE Review

Lade Jayahari et.al [1] **Deep drawing in AISI 304: a finite element simulation study at different temperatures (2014)**. The purpose of this article is to examine the austenitic stainless steel 304's formability at a variety of temperatures just below the warm conditions. Deeply drawn cups may reveal a material's malleability when their draw percentage and thickness dispersion are calculated at room temperature or 1500C. The limiting drawing ratio (LDR) for 1mm thick sheets of austenitic stainless steel 304 at room temperature is 2.1, whereas the LDR for 1mm thick sheets at 1500C is 2.5, with no further growth in LDR at higher temperatures.

R. Venkat Reddy et.al [2] **Impact of Multiple Wrinkle Limits on Deep-Drawn Cylindrical Cups (2012)**. This book aims to shed light on BHF, punch radii, die edges, and coefficient of frictions as the most influential factors in the folding of cylindrical components during the deep drawing technique.

Factors such as stress ratios, mechanical characteristics, work piece shape, may all play a role in whether or not wrinkles form in a sheet of material.

Kopinathi Gowtham et.al [3] **Analyzing the Impact of Die Radius on the Deep Drawing Procedure Virtually (2012)**. Purpose of this study is to examine deep drawing procedure by variable die corner radius while keeping the frictional, & blank thickness constant. Modifying die's corner radius has been employed in an analytical, numerical, and exponential evaluation of the CATIA-generated punch, blank thickness geometry, and finite element simulation process. This technique of simulation used AL6061, an aluminum alloy, with a starting diameter of 56mm and a drawing speed of 0.9m/sec.

III. SIMULATION

We'll be using Solid Edge V19 to make the CAD models for this undertaking. STL and AFDEX V16 file formats mimic the deep drawing process. In this endeavor, metal forming software (AFDEX-2016) will be used to design and simulate the forging process. Forging, rolling, extruding, and drawing are just some of the traditional metalworking techniques that may be replicated using the AFDEX general purpose metal forming simulator. AFDEX is theoretically grounded upon FEM. AFDEX can solve the flow and heat transfer problems that arise in metal forming and die structural analysis.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The steps involved in the deep drawing technique are shown in fig.2. We first thought the part was deep drawn, and based on that, SolidEdge was used to create the CAD models of the dies. The.STL file extension is used to save these CAD models. The next step is to load dies into AFDEX for virtual testing. The process of formation is thermal in character and does not produce any visible sparks. Both the process's starting points and ending points are specified. The friction coefficient (0.05, 0.10, and 0.15) and die corner radius (2-8 mm) are the two independent variables in this deep drawing procedure; the ram velocity (230mm/s), Binder holding force (1265N), and meshing (auto) are held constant. We ran a total of 21 iterations and compiled the data.

Figure 2: Steps involved in simulation

Figure 3: Design assembly of cup

Cup and die design assembly is seen in fig. 3. There is a workpiece, a binder, a lower die, and an upper die all part of the assembly. Table 1 provides information on the various parts.

Table 1: Particulars of Component

Component	Cup
Material Used	AISI 304
Forming Type	Cold
Number of draws	1
Initial Billet Temperature	25°C

A. CAD Modeling

Preparing the component model in Solid edge is a crucial step in the process. The figure below shows a cross-sectional and isometric perspective of the dies and blank.

Figure 4: Blank

Figure 5: Lower Die

Figure 6: Upper Die

Figure 7: Binder

Table 2: AA 6061 Material Properties

Ultimate tensile strength	505Mpa
Modulus of elasticity	193Gpa
Poisson's ratio	0.265
Yield tensile strength	205Mpa
Hardness, <u>Brinell</u>	201
Density	8g/cc

V. RESULTS

Table 3: Damage values for numerous Ram velocity

SL. NO.	Co-efficient of Friction (μ)	Die Corner Radius	Damage Value
1	0.05	2	5.89008E-001
2		3	3.55332E-001
3		4	3.23480E-001
4		5	2.78191E-001
5		6	2.63095E-001
6		7	2.52708E-001
7		8	2.36616E-001
8		0.10	2
9	3		3.98472E-001
10	4		3.20442E-001
11	5		2.96434E-001
12	6		2.55663E-001
13	7		2.65966E-001
14	8		2.35929E-001
15	0.15	2	5.95502E-001
16		3	3.77201E-001
17		4	3.28264E-001
18		5	2.97951E-001
19		6	2.63372E-001
20		7	2.66571E-001
21		8	2.48311E-001

A total of 21 iterations were run, & resulting damage values are shown in Table 3. The data below show the minimum values for three iterations of both damage and load.

Figure 8: Cup damage at 0.05 Coefficient of friction and 8mm die corner radius.

Figure 9: Cup drawing damage at 0.10 friction coefficient and 8mm radius corner die.

Figure 10: Cup damage drawn via 0.15 friction coefficient and 8mm die corner radius.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In the AFDEX software, we ran twenty-one iterations, collecting data by tweaking settings like the die's corner radius and friction coefficient. The BHF and the speed of the punch were both held constant.

Damage value discovered to be minimal in 14th iteration based on above iterations. Coefficient of friction = 0.1 and die corner radius = 8mm yielded a damage value of 2.35929E-001.

The analysis of this iteration made use of the following parameters,

- BHF = 1265N
- Ram Velocity = 230 mm/sec
- Friction co-efficient = 0.10
- Temperature = 25° C

The following inferences may be made from these results,

- ❖ The frictional coefficient is a key factor in the deep drawing process. At 0.10, damage is at its lowest. The cost of damage grows in tandem with the coefficient of friction's magnitude.
- ❖ Damage tends to go down as the square root of the die's corner radius rises. Therefore, the effect of creasing and tearing is reduced. For an 8mm radius at a die's corner, the damage value is at its lowest.
- ❖ As there's no folding on the surface or inside the component, the finished deep drawn cup will be flawless. Therefore, using the aforementioned parameters, a perfect component can be designed.

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